

reduced density (ρ^*) can be chosen as a convenient reduced parameter for comparing the nature of packing in liquids. Such a procedure brings the density of the liquids into a comparable magnitude range. We have calculated V_w from the bond distances and van der Waal radii tabulated by Bondi⁵. The packing density for all the compounds just above the melting point fall in the expected range of 0.64 predicted for low temperature packing of spherical molecules under atmospheric pressure, i.e., the compounds are at corresponding states. Bondi⁵ defined a reduced

parameter $T^* = \frac{5cRT}{E_{\text{vap}}}$, where E_{vap} is the energy of vaporisation at a standard state defined as the temperature at which $\frac{V}{V_w} = 1.70$. The number of degrees

of freedom (3c) of a polyatomic molecule reduces to a value of 6 for rigid molecules. Plot of ρ^* versus T^* in the case of non-linear rigid molecules are expected to fall on one line. Plot of our experimental ρ^* - data for nitrotoluenes⁶, (Fig. 2) is linear with T^* ,

Fig. 2. Reduced Density of Nitrotoluene Melts at Various Temperatures.

within the accuracy with which V_w and E_{vap} could be computed. Thus in the liquid state immediately above their melting point, these compounds behave normally in spite of expected strong intermolecular interactions. In fact, there is no difference between the *o*-isomer, where intramolecular hydrogen bonding should be significant and the *m*- and *p*-isomers, where intermolecular interactions should predominate. This means that the type of associations formed have little bearing on the packing.

The volume changes on melting along with ΔH_m and $\Delta S_m/R$ values obtained by cryoscopy are given in Table 1. All the compounds under study show a

TABLE 1— ΔV_m , ΔH_m AND $\Delta S_m/R$ VALUES

Compounds	ΔV_m ml/mole	ΔH_m K cal/mole	$\Delta S_m/R$
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	9.10	3.73	5.90
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	9.3	4.83	6.60
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	9.0	4.82	6.27
<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene	9-10	3.68	5.71

$\Delta V_m \sim 9-10$ ml/mole. Thus studies on thermodynamics of melting and packing as indicated by density measurements do not seem to reflect the differences between the isomers.

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Solubilization of 9, 10 Diphenyl anthracene in Surfactant Micelle with the Help of Fluorescence Studies

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IN this communication we report solubilization studies of 9, 10 diphenylanthracene (9, 10 DPA) in presence of surfactants with the help of fluorescence spectroscopy. Preliminary observations have already been reported earlier¹ in which it was shown that enhancement in fluorescence of 9, 10 DPA takes place on the addition of surfactants.

It has been found by fluorescence studies that anionic, cationic as well as non-ionic surfactants have solubilizing influence on 9, 10 DPA. Addition of ethanol also causes enhancement in fluorescence intensity of 9, 10 DPA.

Experimental

Fluorescence studies were made on Aminco-Bowman spectrofluorophotometer with Xenon arc

lamp as light source. The slit width for excitation and emission was kept at 0.1 mm and cell of 1 cm path length was used.

The stock solution of analytically pure grade 9, 10 DPA (Schuchardt Munchen, Germany) was prepared in distilled ethanol. All the experiments were made at room temperature (20-22°) and were performed in presence of 20 or 30% ethanol keeping the final concentration of 9, 10 DPA at $10^{-5}M$.

The following surfactants were used :

- (a) *Anionic* :
- (i) Dodecyl benzene sodium sulphonate (DBSS);
 - (ii) Dioctylsodium sulphosuccinate (DSSS).

(b) *Cationic* :

- (i) Cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB);
- (ii) Cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB).

(c) *Non-ionic* :

- (i) Polyoxyethylene ter-octyl phenol (Eq-10) (Tx-100);
- (ii) Polyoxyethylene (23) lauryl ether (Brij-35);
- (iii) Polyoxyethylene sorbitan mono-laurate (Tween-20);
- (iv) Polyoxyethylene sorbitan monopalmitate (Tween-40);
- (v) Polyoxyethylene sorbitan monooleate (Tween-80).

All surfactants were 'Sigma' (USA) or BDH products and were used as such. The purity of the surfactants was checked by determining their cmc values by surface tension measurements employing drop weight method. The values thus obtained are compared with the reported²⁻⁵ ones in Table 1.

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF cmc VALUES OBSERVED AND CITED IN LITERATURE

Sl. No.	Name of surfactant	Reported value	Observed value
1.	Triton X-100	$2.6 \times 10^{-4}M$	$1.6 \times 10^{-4}M$
2.	Brij-35	—	$1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$
3.	Tween-20	5.0×10^{-3} gm/lit	4.0×10^{-3} gm/lit
4.	Tween-40	—	5.0×10^{-3} gm/lit
5.	Tween-80	3.0×10^{-3} gm/lit	2.5×10^{-3} gm/lit
6.	CTAB	$8.0 \times 10^{-4}M$	$6.0 \times 10^{-4}M$
7.	CPB	$1.23 \times 10^{-3}M$	$1.33 \times 10^{-3}M$
8.	DBSS	—	6.0×10^{-3} gm/lit

Results and Discussion

The maximum excitation wave lengths were at 364 and 384 nm. The emission spectrum in 20% ethanol showed three peaks at 410, 430 and 465 nm, while in 30% ethanol only two peaks at 410 and 430 nm were observed.

All the surfactants caused enhancement in the fluorescence intensity of 9, 10 DPA. Studies made

with various types of surfactants are given below :

In presence of 20% ethanol, the peak at 465 nm disappeared, at higher concentration of surfactant, while enhancement occurred in the height of peaks at 410 and 430 nm. The peak heights reached their limiting values at higher concentrations of all the non-ionic and anionic surfactants while observations at higher concentration of cationic surfactants could not be taken due to their low solubility at room temperature. Thus the limiting values of peak heights could not be reached when cationic surfactants were employed. The amount of surfactant needed to reach the limited value varied with each surfactant.

The fluorescence spectra at different concentrations of Tx-100 in 20% ethanolic medium are given in Fig. 1. All other surfactants showed similar influence. In 30% ethanolic medium only two prominent peaks were observed at 410 nm and 430 nm as given in Fig. 2. The peak height increased on addition of all the three types of the surfactants.

Fig. 1. Changes in fluorescence spectra of 9, 10 DPA on adding Tx-100 in 20% ethanolic medium $\lambda_{ex}=364$ nm.

- 9, 10 DPA ($10^{-5}M$)
- 9, 10 DPA with 0.05% Tx-100
- ×—× 9, 10 DPA with 0.60% Tx-100

Effect of Ethanol : Enhancement in fluorescence intensity was also observed on adding ethanol to a solution of 9, 10 DPA. This effect was more pronounced above 30% ethanolic medium and the fluorescence intensity reached its maximum value in presence of 50% ethanol.

Fig. 2. Changes in fluorescence spectra of 9, 10 DPA on adding Tween-20 in 30% ethanolic medium.

$\lambda_{ex} = 364 \text{ nm}$
 ●—● 9, 10 DPA ($10^{-6} M$)
 ○—○ 9, 10 DPA with 0.005% Tween-20
 ×—× 9, 10 DPA with 0.300% Tween-20.

Enhancement in fluorescence intensity on addition of non-ionic, anionic and cationic surfactants as well as on addition of ethanol are indicated in Fig. 3. It can be observed that large and sudden

Fig. 3. (i) Variations in fluorescence intensity of 9, 10 DPA in 20% ethanolic medium

($\lambda_{ex} = 364 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{em} = 412 \text{ nm}$).
 (A) Varying the concentration of Tx-100
 (B) Varying the concentration of DBSS
 (C) Varying the concentration of CTAB

(ii) (D) Influence of ethanol concentration on the fluorescence intensity of 9, 10 DPA.
 cmc values are marked by arrow \otimes →.

increase in fluorescence intensity occurred near the cmc of the surfactant.

These observations can be explained on the basis of solubilizing action of the surfactants and also of ethanol. The enhancement in the fluorescence intensity on the addition of surfactant in 20% and 30% ethanolic medium appears to be due to the solubilization of 9, 10 DPA in the surfactant micelle since large enhancement in fluorescence intensity occurs in the cmc region of the concerned surfactant.

It appears that 9, 10 DPA is not fully solubilized in 20% ethanolic medium, since the fluorescence intensity reaches a limiting value only in presence of 50% or higher ethanolic concentration. The diminished effect of the surfactant in presence of higher ethanolic concentration is due to the destruction of surfactant micelle⁶⁻⁸.

The shape of fluorescence spectra remains unchanged during the addition of surfactants or ethanol. This indicates that the molecules of 9, 10 DPA undergo no change in size or geometry during these processes and only solubilization of the colloidal particles occurs during these reactions.

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Note on the Separation of 2 : 4-Dinitrophenol and Picric Acid by Column Chromatography

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In a previous communication, the authors¹ have reported on the development of anion-exchange properties of Brockmann alumina, on pretreatment with HCl acid at low pH values ($pH < 5.5$). It was

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